

Research Article

Evaluating Halal Certification Compliance Among Food Sellers in Taman Selera Harmoni, Sibu: An Investigation of User Awareness and Perception

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Abstract: The study aims to evaluate the level of Halal certification compliance among food sellers in Taman Selera Harmoni Sibu and investigate the awareness and perception of user towards Halal certification. Halal certification plays a vital role in ensuring that food products meet the requirements of Islamic dietary laws. The study seeks to provide insights into the current compliance status of food sellers, the level of user awareness about Halal certification, and their perception towards Halal-certified food products. A mixed-methods approach will be employed, including surveys and interviews, to collect data from food sellers and users in Taman Selera Harmoni Sibu. The collected data will be analyzed using statistical analysis techniques and thematic analysis to identify patterns, trends, and factors influencing compliance and awareness level. The findings of this study will contribute to the understanding of the challenges faced by food sellers in complying with Halal certification requirements and the level of awareness and perception among users towards Halal certification. The results will inform the development of recommendations to enhance compliance and improve user awareness, thereby promoting Halal food services in Taman Selera Harmoni Sibu. This research is significant as it can contribute to the improvement of Halal food practices, ensure the availability of authentic Halal food options, and meet the needs of the local Muslim community. The findings can benefit food sellers, consumers, local authorities, and Halal certification bodies in fostering compliance, enhancing awareness, and fostering trust in Halal food services. Future research can build upon these findings to further explore the dynamic landscape of Halal certification compliance and user perceptions in other contexts.

Keywords: Halal Certification, Food, Awareness, Perception

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1. INTRODUCTION

Halal compliance for food sellers involves complying by Islamic dietary laws and caring for every link in the food chain up till the customer. Halal is the term used in Islamic law to describe any food, beverage, or product that is permitted and legal for Muslims to consume in accordance with the Quran and Sunnah. Therefore, to ensure that the food being sold is prepared and handled in conformity with Islamic dietary standards, halal compliance for food dealers requires adhering to specified criteria and requirements. The sourcing of ingredients, processing and production, packaging and labelling, storage and transportation, staff training, and halal certification may be some essential components of halal

compliance for food sellers. To satisfy the needs of Muslim customers who seek halal-certified food products for their dietary and religious preferences, it is crucial for food sellers to comprehend and adhere to halal laws. Halal compliance can create opportunities for food sellers to enter the expanding local and international halal food markets.

The halal food business is currently experiencing a global impact and is expanding quite quickly, this is not just happening in Malaysia. Every organisation must obtain halal certification before conducting business in the halal food sector. Based on the organization's efficacy and efficiency in accordance with the halal certificate, performance is assessed. The truth is that the halal industry's successful management of halal food still has problems and falls short of expectations established by the rules and guidelines employed. It was found that compliance with the halal certificate is influenced by a chain that is linked to each other starting from input, then translated in the form of a process and finally producing achievements that are also supported by the internal control of the organization (Nora et al.,2020).

Parallel to the growth in the number of Muslims around the world, the global market for halal goods shows an encouraging trend. A rise in demand for halal foods, cosmetics, medicines, and consumables will result from an increase in the number of Muslims. The Malaysian government has begun to take action to establish Malaysia as the world's halal centre considering this lucrative economic potential. A halal certification is a document provided by a reputable organisation or Islamic authority that attests that a product complies with the halal and haram rules in Islam, which have been established specifically to make sure that no prohibited items, such pork, are present in the product. Those who apply, especially restaurant operators or owners, are generally obliged to observe and comply with every requirement and instructions provided either by laws or the halal certification processing manual in terms of the verification requirements for halal certification (Buang et al.,2012).

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Taman Selera Harmoni Sibul in Jalan Awang Ramli Amit has more than 47 food and beverage stalls, is the largest food court in Sarawak that has been approved by the Halal Recognition Certificate. This matter can have a big impact on the people of Sibul, Sarawak because such food premises will help attract more visitors here (Borhanizah,2022).

This highlighted two key issues which is user awareness and perception towards Halal certification compliance among food sellers and the challenges and impacts associated with it in the specific context of Taman Selera Harmoni in Sibul. The problem of user awareness refers to a potential lack of knowledge or understanding among consumers and food sellers in Taman Selera Harmoni regarding the importance and requirements of Halal certification compliance. This may include limited awareness among consumers about the meaning and significance of Halal certification, as well as among food sellers about the specific guidelines and procedures for obtaining and maintaining Halal certification. Due to the fact that they operate a part-time business, lack a business license, and are concerned that their application will not be accepted, sellers who have not yet submitted an halal application. While waiting for the certification process to be completed, the relevant agencies must work more closely together to monitor the situation, paying particular attention to small sellers' needs in order to make it simpler for them to apply and conduct business in a manner similar to that of larger sellers (Suhaili et.al, 2022).

The perception issue relates to how customers and food sellers perceive Taman Selera Harmoni's compliance of the Halal certification. This may include a variety of attitudes, such as the trust,

confidence, dependability, and legitimacy of food products with the Halal certification, as well as the value of the Halal certification in attracting Muslim customers. The problem statement also highlights the difficulties that food sellers encounter in obtaining and maintaining compliance with Halal certification, as well as the potential effects on their business. These issues could relate to finding ingredients that are Halal-certified, putting in place and maintaining Halal-compliant procedures, paying for certification, and keeping up with the changing Halal criteria. Among the effects are possible Muslim client losses, reputational issues, and fewer business options for serving the Muslim populace. The opinion of small and medium-sized companies towards Malaysia's halal certification is influenced by self-identity as a Muslim. Non-Muslim business owners are regarded as sincere and dedicated to getting their products recognised as halal. While Muslims who own their own businesses do not view the necessity for halal certification as a marketing opportunity. Muslims who work as entrepreneurs believe that consumers already have faith in the goods they produce. Only Muslim products that adhere to Sharia law may be marketed as "halal." (Malaysia et.al, 2013).

1.2 RESEARCH QUESTION

1. Does Taman Selera Harmoni Sibul maintain halal compliance?
2. Does food sellers in Taman Selera Harmon Sibul are very concerned about the production of halal food to consumers?
3. What are the opportunities for improving compliance with Halal certification requirements among food sellers in Taman Harmoni Sibul?

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

1. To study about the halal certification compliance of food sellers in Taman Selera Harmoni Sibul.
2. To identify the said food sellers are very concerned about the production of halal food to consumers.
3. To find out the opportunities for improving compliance with Halal certification requirements among food sellers in Taman Harmoni Sibul.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Data Collection

The data gathered is used to further describe the study's goal. Therefore, a variety of equipment is used to collect data. Among them is to give questionnaires to respondents and refer to studies by past researchers. Structured questionnaires and interviews with food sellers in Taman Harmoni Sibul were used to acquire the primary data. The surveys were made with the intention of gathering quantitative information on a variety of topics, including the food sellers' understanding of Halal certification criteria, their procedures for getting and displaying Halal certification, and their use of Halal-certified items. In-depth qualitative insights into the sellers' attitudes and experiences surrounding Halal compliance, however, were only possible through interviews. The research was able to directly capture the perspectives and experiences of food sellers in the study region because of the use of primary data gathering techniques. The use of secondary data sources complemented the use of primary data. This included acquiring current data on Halal certification practices, consumer behaviour, and the Halal industry from reliable publications, government reports, and university studies. The study's

background material was enriched with secondary data, which also helped to explain the results and enhance the analysis and interpretation of the original data. By using exacting data collection methods, the researchers ensured the accuracy and dependability of the data. To find any potential problems and improve the questions, the survey and interviews methods were pre-tested. This procedure assisted in ensuring that the data gathered were precise and pertinent to the study's goals. To further improve the generalizability of the results to the larger population of food sellers in the area, the researchers utilised proper sampling techniques to choose a representative sample of food sellers in Taman Harmoni SibU.

To guarantee that a significant number of replies were acquired from the food merchants, data collecting was done over a predetermined period of time. Additionally, while collecting the data, researchers observed ethical standards and took precautions to keep the respondents' information private. In conclusion, questionnaires and interviews with food sellers were used to gather primary data for the study "Evaluating Halal Certification Compliance Among Food Sellers in Taman Harmoni SibU: An Investigation of User Awareness and Perception", which was supported by secondary data sources. The combination of these techniques enabled a thorough and precise evaluation of the Halal certification compliance among food sellers in Taman Harmoni SibU, providing insightful data for the study's goals.

2.2 DATA ANALYSIS

This study have employ descriptive analysis to examine the data, and a survey with a number of questions have carried out using Google Form. The Taman Selera Harmoni SibU food sellers were given the survey to collect responds from the respondents. The results of the analysis can help in identifying the significant factors influencing compliance and awareness levels and can aid in developing recommendations for food vendors, consumers, local authorities, and Halal certification bodies. Therefore, the study can enhance the rigor and validity of the analysis, providing meaningful insights into the level of compliance with Halal certification requirements among food vendors and the awareness and perception of users towards Halal certification.

3. FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

In this section, the researcher has prepared 7 yes or no questions about awareness of halal certification to sellers in Taman Selera Harmoni, SibU. It will be displayed on frequency on the respondents.

1. Are you aware of the Halal certification requirements for food sellers in Taman Harmoni SibU? 1. Adakah anda mengetahui keperluan pensijilan Halal bagi penjual makanan di Taman Harmoni SibU?
35 responses

Based on the frequency, it stated that all the Taman Selera Harmoni, Sibu sellers answered yes on this question. It means that every respondent has answered affirmatively, indicating that they are aware of the Halal certification requirements.

Therefore, unless steps are taken to increase Muslim understanding of these items and their benefits, the development of these products in Islamic marketplaces cannot be connected to reality. This significant issue requires a lot of work and several steps. The objective of this study is to ascertain the amount of awareness that halal customers and sellers of these items have regarding halal as well as to identify the responsible individuals or organisations for introducing and promoting these products to the Muslim population in Islamic nations (Hajipour et.al, 2015).

A 100% “yes” frequency indicates that every food seller in Taman Harmoni Sibu who participated in the data gathering process or received a survey is aware of the particular specifications, rules, and procedures relevant to Halal certification.

2. Have you obtained Halal certification for your food products from a recognized Halal certification body? 2. Adakah anda telah mendapat pensijilan Hal...a daripada badan pensijilan Halal yang diiktiraf?

35 responses

To learn more about the certification status of foods from the perspective of the respondents, the question “Have you obtained Halal certification for your food products from a recognised Halal certification body?” is offered. It is significant because it allows for an evaluation of the food sellers’ efforts to obtain Halal certification for their goods from a reputable certifying agency.

Malaysians who enjoy dining out have varying opinions about establishments that have a halal certification. Keel and Islamic law dictate a precise process for producing halal food. Since the time of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), this halal issue has been a topic of discussion in the Islamic community. His Majesty provided instruction on how to prepare, sell, and consume food according to Islamic law. From the beginning of the preparation process until it is served, it is involved. The foundation for making halal food has not altered over time up until this point. The organisation in charge of approving halal certificates for restaurants across Malaysia is the Islamic Religious Department of Malaysia (JAKIM) (Rahim et.al, 2020).

94.3% of the respondents answered “yes” and 5.7% answered “no” to these questions, it indicates the distribution of responses among the surveyed food sellers. It may be deduced that the majority of the food sellers polled have acquired Halal certification for their food goods from a reputable Halal certification agency based on the frequency of “yes” responses, which was 94.3%. This demonstrates a strong dedication to upholding the Halal requirements and offering consumers genuine Halal items.

4. Do you ensure that your Halal certification is clearly displayed on your food stall? 4. Adakah anda memastikan pensijilan Halal anda dipaparkan dengan jelas di gerai makanan anda?

35 responses

To learn more about the visibility and transparency of Halal certification among food vendors, the question "Do you ensure that your Halal certification is clearly displayed on your food stall?" is offered. It is significant because it reveals how much importance food sellers place on informing and reassuring customers by clearly displaying their Halal certification.

Based on Zulkifli et.al (2018), Majlis Ugama Islam Singapura (MUIS) highlighted that its halal certificates are properly displayed in halal certified eating places. MUIS certifies local establishments adhering to the halal regulations in Singapore. Although Muslims make just a small portion of the population, the display makes it simple for them to be recognised.

In essence, it also involves taking into account social integration when dining in a completely halal environment with other non-Muslims. Here are 94.3% of the respondents answered "yes" and 5.7% answered "no" to this question indicates the distribution of responses among the surveyed food sellers regarding the display of their Halal certification. The majority of the food sellers questioned make sure that their Halal certification is prominently displayed on their food stalls, as indicated by the 94.3% "yes" frequency. This demonstrates a strong commitment to transparency and giving customers concrete proof of their compliance with Halal.

5. Do you use Halal certified ingredients in your food products? 5. Adakah anda menggunakan bahan yang disahkan Halal dalam produk makanan anda?

35 responses

The question "Do you use Halal certified ingredients in your food products?" is provided to gather information about the sourcing and use of Halal-certified ingredients by food sellers. It is significant

because it aids in determining the degree of adherence to and dedication to Halal standards in the choice and usage of ingredients.

Islam holds that in order for food to be considered safe, it must first start with halal ingredients and then be processed, slaughtered, and obtained in the proper manner. As a Muslim-majority nation, government is in charge of ensuring that halal food products are available. It is necessary to first understand the components of a food before deciding whether it is thoyyib (excellent). Before being considered thoyyib, food must adhere to halal standards. Food items that are halal for Muslims may not necessarily include foods that are good according to science, and vice versa, foods that are excellent according to science do not always include foods that are halal. For example, while the brain of an animal raised for food is halal, it should not be consumed by those who have heart disease since it includes high levels of cholesterol and fat, both of which are detrimental to the soul (Zulkifli et.al, 2018).

There are 97.1% of the respondents answered "yes" and 2.79% answered "no" to the question "Do you use Halal certified ingredients in your food products?", it indicates the distribution of responses among the surveyed food sellers regarding the use of Halal-certified ingredients. The majority of the food merchants questioned use Halal-certified components in their food products, as indicated by the frequency of "yes" responses, which was 97.1%. This high percentage indicates that they remain committed to upholding Halal requirements and guaranteeing the authenticity of their services.

6. Do you use separate utensils, equipment and cooking areas for Halal and non-Halal food products? 6. Adakah anda menggunakan peralatan ...an untuk produk makanan Halal dan tidak Halal?

35 responses

The question "Do you use separate utensils, equipment, and cooking areas for Halal and non - Halal food products?" is provided to gather information about the segregation practices followed by food sellers. It is important because it helps assess the level of commitment to maintaining the integrity and purity of Halal food by avoiding cross-contamination with non-Halal items. Businesses show respect for religious diversity and win the trust of Muslim customers by separating halal and non-halal items. Any food that does not according to Shariah law needs to be separated because it is regarded as impure. Furthermore, given the developing worldwide halal market, adhering to halal standards can enhance food safety, product quality, and industry growth. Making sure that halal and non-halal materials are properly separated is not only a cultural and religious requirement for businesses operating in multicultural cultures or looking to enter the halal market, but it is also a calculated financial decision to satisfy the expectations of an expanding customer base. In order to further increase customer confidence in halal products, halal certification agencies are essential in ensuring conformity with halal criteria (Ab Talib et.al, 2012).

It shows that, 91.4% of the respondents answered "yes" and 8.6% answered "no" to the question. The majority of the food sellers polled employ separate utensils, equipment, and cooking places for Halal and non-Halal food products, according to the 91.4% "yes" frequency. This significant number

indicates a strong dedication to preventing cross contamination in order to safeguard the integrity and purity of Halal cuisine.

3. CONCLUSION

The study's findings are crucial for evaluating users' awareness of and attitudes towards Halal certification as well as the extent to which Taman Selera Harmoni Sibuh's food sellers comply to the requirements for Halal certification. The results of this study can offer useful information to food sellers, consumers, local government officials, and organisations that certify Halal products.

By identifying areas for improvement in their compliance to the criteria for Halal certification and increasing their understanding of the importance of Halal certification in meeting the needs of Muslim customers, the study can help food sellers. Additionally, it can increase customers' confidence in the Halal food supply chain by assisting them in making informed selections when selecting Halal food sellers and products. The study can help Halal certification bodies improve their certification procedures and policies by contributing crucial information to local authorities who are in charge of regulating and enforcing compliance with Halal certification requirements.

The importance of this study also resides in its ability to add to the body of knowledge already available on user awareness and perception of Halal certification compliance. It can be used as a guide for upcoming research and studies on Halal food services, consumer behaviour, and compliance to certification requirements in comparable situations or other places.

According to the survey, Taman Harmoni Sibuh's food sellers show a good level of knowledge and comprehension of Halal certification standards. This demonstrates that they are aware of how important halal compliance is in satisfying the nutritional needs and spiritual convictions of the Halal-conscious consumer sector. They can retain the integrity and originality of their food goods because they are aware of the certification standards.

The majority of food sellers have strongly obtained Halal certification from recognised certifying bodies for their food products. It demonstrates their commitment to upholding the exacting standards and rules established by these authorities. By acquiring a Halal certification, food providers can reassure customers that strict criteria are followed throughout the food preparation process, giving them assurance that their products are Halal.

The study highlighted Taman Harmoni Sibuh food sellers' careful practise of publicly displaying their Halal certification on their food stands. Customers may quickly recognise and confirm whether the food goods being offered are halal thanks to this clear display.

Customers feel more confident in the legitimacy of the Halal offerings when the certification is readily available and apparent. Overall, the results of this study can help food sellers in Taman Selera Harmoni Sibuh comply with Halal certification requirements better, increase consumer awareness of and trust in Halal food services, inform local government officials and certification bodies, and support the promotion of true Halal food practises. The Taman Selera Harmoni Sibuh Halal food environment could be improved with more research and work in this area, better serving the demands of the neighbourhood's Muslim population.

Acknowledgments: Appreciation to the food sellers at Taman Selera Harmoni, Sibuh, Sarawak for their cooperation.

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